

A Study on the Role of Social Entrepreneurship in Economic Development

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Introduction :

Vital to economic growth and inclusion, especially for developing economies, social entrepreneurship a fast emerging discipline that generates social impact through an entrepreneurial approach helps to boost a country's economy, as well as its social fabric. Social enterprises can create jobs, provide innovative services and products, promote sustainability and give hope for the future. According to the European Commission, the social entrepreneurship sector currently employs around 40 million people and engages over 200 million volunteers globally and is growing. Social enterprises are not just for emerging markets, however.

Concept of Social Entrepreneurship :

Social entrepreneurship is the use of the techniques that startup companies and other entrepreneurs to develop, fund and implement solutions to social, cultural, or environmental issues.

Definition of Social entrepreneurship :

Creating and seizing an opportunity and pursuing it regardless of the resources currently controlled, it is a human creative act, it usually requires a vision, it involves building a team of sensing opportunities and finding and marshalling resources and ensuring the venture does not run out of money.

History :

Social Entrepreneurship is relatively a new term. It came in to notice just a few decades ago. But its usage can be found throughout the history. In fact, there were several entrepreneurs who established social entrepreneurs to eliminate social problems or bring positive change in the society. Vinoba Bhave, the founder of India's Land Gift Movement, Robert Owen, the founder of cooperative movement and Florence Nightingale, founder of first nursing school and developer of modern nursing practices might be included in this category. They had established such foundations and organizations in 19th century that is much before the concept of social entrepreneurship used in management.

Role of Social Entrepreneurship :**➤ Employment Development :**

The first major economic value that social entrepreneurship creates is the job and employment. Estimates range from one to seven percent of people employed in the social entrepreneurship sector.

➤ Innovation :

New Goods and Services Social entrepreneurs develop and apply innovation important to social and economic development and develop new goods and services. Issues addressed include some of the biggest societal problems such as HIV, mental ill-health, illiteracy, crime and drug abuse which, importantly are confronted in innovative ways.

➤ Equity Promotion :

Social entrepreneurship fosters a more equitable society by addressing social issues and trying to achieve ongoing sustainable impact through their social mission

rather than purely profit-maximization. Another case is the American social entrepreneur J.B. Schramm who has helped thousands of low-income high-school students to get into tertiary education.

Qualities of Social Entrepreneurs :

➤ Curiosity :

Social entrepreneurs must nurture a sense of curiosity about people and the problems they face. The best social entrepreneurs seek to truly understand the needs and desires of the people they serve. Great social ventures often start through immersive market research, an empathy-centric process through which social entrepreneurs gain knowledge in the field.

➤ Inspiration :

In order to design effective solutions, social entrepreneurs must be inspired by the people and problems they encounter. Inspiration motivates action and helps social entrepreneurs tackle challenges that others shy away from addressing.

➤ Resourcefulness :

In the world of social entrepreneurship, key resources, such as human and financial capital, can often be scarce. Successful social entrepreneurs know how to leverage the resources at their disposal and develop innovative methods to overcome obstacles.

➤ Openness to Collaboration :

While embarking on a quest to change the world may feel lonely, it is important to remember that social entrepreneurship is a team sport, and other people are willing to help. Social entrepreneurs need to stay open and attentive to potential partnership and collaboration opportunities. In many cases, collaborative initiatives and joint-ventures can achieve social/business goals much more effectively than solo endeavors.

➤ Persistence :

Social entrepreneurs take on some of the most daunting challenges our society has to offer. This often creates a recipe for early-stage failures. However,

the successful social entrepreneurs are the ones who persist past initial setbacks and persevere to deliver effective solutions.

Conclusion :

Social ventures will vary depending on the different cultures and political environments from where they sprout. One constant, however, is the role they play in transforming societies. Social entrepreneurship is a commitment to the process of change and the creation of new social value. These ventures provide fertile grounds for the next generations to re-imagine and mold their societies accordingly. Their work will embolden global vision of economic equality and the alleviation of poverty.

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